

HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' VIOLENCE TENDENCIES

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Abstract:

This paper aimed to compare the levels of violence tendency in three different types of high schools. The universe of the research consisted of the high school students in the province Konya, the sample group involved 280 male, 224 female students studying at the Vocational, Anatolian and Sport High Schools. In obtaining data, a personal information form and the Violence Tendency Scale (VTS) developed by Göka et al. (1995) were used. The scale was made up of a four-point Likert type with 20 questions, varying from (1) "absolutely inappropriate" to (4) "absolutely appropriate". The highest point from the scale was "80", the lowest point was "1". A high point shows that the students' aggressiveness and violence tendencies are more. In accordance with the students' points from the scale, the point between 1-20 as "very poor", the point between 21-40 as "poor", the point between 41-60 as "good" and the point between 61-80 as "very good" were regarded in terms of violence tendency, the "Cronbach Alpha" reliability coefficient of the scale was found to be .88. By testing the homogeneity and variance of data, in the determination of statistical differences Independent t-test, One Way Anova, Tukey-HSD tests were utilised. In this paper, the male students' violence tendency averages were higher rather than the female students and this difference was statistically significant ($P<0.05$). The values regarding the students doing sportive activities were lower than the students not doing sport and this difference was statistically significant ($P<0.05$). Depending on the factors of father and mother's education level, income level and class, any statistical differences were not observed. The Sport High School students' violence tendency averages were lower than two other school types, the difference between the sport high school and the vocational high

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school was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). In conclusion, the students who give importance to sportive activities in their lives and have sportive education, are considered to have lower violence tendency rather than the students at other schools.

Keywords: violence, anger, aggressiveness, high school student

1. Introduction

Literature is highly rich in violence and violence related concepts. In general terms, it represents to have excessive feelings and behaviours, use brute force against persons having different opinions from oneself (TDK access, 2017; Budak, 2003; Çabuk Kaya, 2006). Ayan (2007) describes violence as expressing, reflecting aggressiveness tendency which is accepted to be naturally present in persons, individuals or social dimensions by damaging to other persons. The violence case has carried various meanings in its own approaches, its own scientific fields, under the social and historical conditions (Tor and Sargin, 2005).

The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that violence which is regarded to be injured against a person, a group or a society, resort to physical power or threat resulting from death, psychological damage and depression, is experienced in lots of emotional, physical, verbal, sexual and political dimensions (WHO, 2002). Violence is a social case changing in society and in time whatever its basic characteristics are. Like a violent event can have various meanings in different societies, it can be perceived in different ways in the same society in different times. Societies change, furthermore, social norms change as well (TBMM Research Report, 2013).

Whatever the resource and reason of violence is; it carries damaging features against an individual committing violence, its directed object, a living and a social structure. It can be physical, furthermore, any word, any approach, any attitude, any manner which bring psychological aggressiveness and violence to mind, are the determinants of violence level. Memiş et al. (2013) divides violence into three classes of physical, verbal-psychological and sexual ones. In WHO's report (2002), violence was defined in three groups including self-directed, interpersonal and collective violence in terms of violence-oriented persons.

Another classification is available in literature, this one involves physical violence (hustling and bustling, beating, shooting, slapping, kicking, stabbing), sexual violence (raping, forcing into marriage or giving in early marriage, snipping, forcing sexual relations by using brute force/emotional power), emotional power (insulting, swearing, humiliating, continuously criticising, ironising, nicknaming, socially isolating, not showing love, mobbing, snubbing) and economic violence (managing,

dispossessing a person's money by force) which occur with the negative reasons of biological, psychological and social factors (Prime Ministry Family Research Report, 1998; TBMM Research Commission, 2007).

With the rapid development of current technology, social sensitivity and shares have increasingly reduced. Virtual activities and shares designed in the web environment via computer networks have replaced many social and cultural activities. Visual perception has made violence epidemic, and especially it has been considered as ordinary by children. Anyway; it would not be wrong to say that visual machines take parents' places. In particular, physical violence is reflected as a normal situation and a feeling product in the children's world. In literature many researches show that the perception of physical violence is much more common in the children's lives rather than the other types of violence (Hiçyılmaz et al. 2015; Saban and Akbulut, 2012; Özgür et al. 2011; Deveci et al. 2008).

The concept of "Violence at School"; represents offense-focused actions and aggressiveness which obstruct developing and learning, give damage to the school atmosphere (Furlong and Morrison, 2000). In TBMM Research Commission (2007) report, the students studying at the high schools experienced violence at streets (39%) at most, at schools and around them (%34). In the world and our country, violence has reached at worrisome levels given its relevant factors. Bandura (1997) paid attention that violence was a learned behaviour and an acquired characteristic. Today children and young people have reflected self-directed violence and aggressiveness on their peers, other individuals and objects, which is regarded to be highly common and usual little events.

The Prime Ministry Family Research Institution (1998) reported that the children subjected to violence by their parents had increasing violent behaviors. It is clear that different results from self-agonising actions to discouragement attempts for life in individuals' self-directed violence appear. Young people's violence practices at schools and in their daily lives are not registered as faults, only the ones engaged in violence and the targets of violence are genuine actors of this situation. Gangs, mafia conflicts and terrorist incidents are collectively seen as another platforms of violence. As Kocacık (2007) stated that groups which recognised each other before, continued on their hostile attitudes even if they could not remember the reasons of their hostile behaviours, the Prime Ministry Family Research Institution (1998) informed that they could display aggressive behaviours to people who they met by chance.

Gelinas (2003) suggested that exposure to violence put children and adolescents at risk in terms of anxiety, depression, fobbies, tactile-perceptual disorders and especially posttraumatic stress problems. When violence is at right form and in right

time, by realising and improving violence, it will contribute to both an individual's physical health and an individual's psychological development.

Education system and programs intend to develop self-confident individuals in order to make right decisions towards children and young people's abilities and make the best selection for themselves. If many feelings such as anger, aggressiveness and violence are not rightly directed and controlled, they will give irremediable damages not only to a person committing violence and being committed violence but also to the whole society. The violence concept is a real case to be dealt in details within the education system.

2. Material and Method

The research was a descriptive type of study and this one aimed to compare the violence tendency levels of three different high schools. The scope of the research consisted of the high school students in the province Konya, the sampling group involved 280 male, 224 female students studying at the Vocational, Anatolian and Sport High Schools.

In obtaining data, a personal information form and the Violence Tendency Scale developed by Göka et al. (1995) were used. The scale was redesigned in the research titled with "Violence in Family and Social Field" (1998) of the T.C. Prime Ministry Family Research Institution without damaging to its basic structure, and its content validity was done. The scale was formed from 20 questions, a four point likert scale changing from (1) "absolutely inappropriate" to (4) "absolutely appropriate". The highest point from the scale was "80", the lowest point was "1". The highest point shows that the students' aggressiveness and violence tendencies are more. In accordance with the students' points from the scale, the point between 1-20 as "very poor", the point between 21-40 as "poor", the point between 41-60 as "good" and the point between 61-80 as "very good" violence tendency were regarded, the "Cronbach Alpha" reliability co-efficient of the scale was .88. In our study, this value was estimated to be .91.

By testing the homogeneity and variance of data, in the determination of statistical differences, Independent t-test, One Way Anova, Tukey-HSD tests were used. For the analysis of relations between the dependent and independent variables, the Multiple Regression Analysis was applied.

3. Findings

Table 1: Depending on the Gender Factor, Differences in Violence Tendency Scale

Gender	n	%	Mean	Ss	t	P
Male	280	55,6	41,30	6,46	3,190	,001*
Female	224	44,4	39,47	6,27		
Sportive Activity						
Doing Sport	255	50,6	39,40	5,87	3,874	,000*
Not Doing Sport	249	49,4	41,59	6,80		

*Significant differences between groups

As seen at Table 1, the male students' violence tendency averages ($41,3 \pm 6,46$) were found to be higher than the averages concerning the females ($39,47 \pm 6,27$), this difference was statistically significant ($P < 0,05$). The values of the students doing sportive activities ($39,4 \pm 5,87$) were lower than the students not doing sportive activities ($41,59 \pm 6,8$) and this difference was also statistically significant ($P < 0,05$).

Table 2: Depending on the School Type, Differences in Violence Tendency

High School Type	n	%	Mean	Ss	F	P
Vocational High School	170	33,7	41,54	6,95 ^a	4,489	,012*
Anatolian High School	215	42,7	40,33	6,21		
Sport High School	119	23,6	39,28	5,86 ^b		
Total	504	100,0	40,49	6,43		

* , a,b = Significant differences between groups

As understood from Table 2, violence tendency averages regarding the Vocational High School students ($41,54 \pm 6,95$) were determined to be higher than the Anatolian High School ($40,43 \pm 6,21$) and Sport High School ($39,24 \pm 5,86$), the difference between Vocational High School and Sport High School students was regarded to be statistically significant ($P < 0,05$).

Table 3: Depending on the Factors of Class, Income Level, Father and Mother Education Level, The Violence Tendencies

Class Level	n	%	Mean	Ss	F	P
9th Class	202	40,1	40,60	6,01	,249	,779
10th Class	231	45,8	40,28	6,90		
11st Class	71	14,1	40,83	6,09		

Income Level						
500-1500 TL	98	19,4	40,33	6,02		
1501-2500 TL	224	44,4	40,38	6,31	,112	,953
2501-3500 TL	65	12,9	40,60	7,64		
3501 TL and over	117	23,2	40,75	6,35		
Father Education Level						
Primary School	174	34,52	40,97	6,15		
Secondary School & High School	146	28,97	40,48	7,27	,649	,584
Higher Education	150	29,76	40,11	5,84		
Master /Doctorate	34	6,75	39,74	6,64		
Mother Education Level						
Primary School	215	42,66	40,68	6,76		
Secondary School & High School	191	37,90	40,32	6,23	,162	,922
Higher Education	89	17,66	40,29	6,15		
Master / Doctorate	9	1,79	41,11	6,17		

As seen at Table 3, depending on the factors of class, income level, father and mother education level, the differences in violence tendency values were not statistically significant ($P>0.05$).

4. Discussion And Conclusion

In this study, the male students' violence tendency averages were higher rather than the female students and this difference was regarded to be statistically significant ($P<0.05$). Many literature studies show that violence levels in the male students were higher than the female students (Koçak, 2017; Sağlam, 2016; Erkek, 2016; Gür, 2015; Nair, 2014; Pekince, 2012; Özgür et al., 2011). Our research findings comply with these studies. Özgür et al. (2011) suggest that as students having violence tendencies and building up a violence risk group, the males had higher averages even though they had few violence experiences. Some studies (Yönet et al. 2016; Hanhan, 2012) indicate that the female students had higher aggressiveness and violence averages rather than the male students even if they were limited.

The students doing sportive activities had lower violence tendency values than the students not doing sport and this difference was statistically significant ($P<0.05$). Balcioğlu (2003) Buluş informed that young people must do physical movements in order to direct their strengths in the current age, organisms must meet their movement needs and emphasized that freedom for movement was limited since children were

always at school. The sport high school students' violence tendency averages were lower than the other two school types, the difference between the sport high school and the vocational high school was statistically significant. Exercise and sportive activities represent a universal fact which facilitates to perceive many abstract concepts such as peace, friendship, brotherhood, love, respect, feeling of share, responsibility-taking, confidence, responsibility, etc. by individuals. The students having sportive capabilities and studying at this field have lower violence tendencies rather than the other schools, which clarifies the importance of sport in young people's lives.

Bakırcıoğlu (2010) mentioned that sport had significant effects on any individual's socialization, one's physical energy increasing in the adolescence period was canalized via exercises in sport. Again, in the same study individuals were socialized, developed personalities compatible with society and exercises were of critical importance for their next lives. These studies have similar characteristics with our findings. In addition to interest and time to sportive activities in the education institutions, when ideal sport managers guide sport, the relevant problems can be overcome. Yönet et al. (2016) emphasized that school directors must take the effects of recreative practices into consideration to prevent the high school students' aggressive behaviours.

In this study any statistical differences were not observed in the factors of father and mother education level, income level and class. In parallel with the homogeneity of student profiles at schools, demographical factors were similar to each other and were not different. The responsible one for violence except for family is society, violence in family is kept as a secret of a special life.

The ones who witness to family violence in their childhood and youth period, are considered to be prone to violence (Kılıçarslan, 2010). According to Martin and Greenwood (1995), mothers-fathers who often perpetrate violence in their relations with other people, allow their children to learn violence (Aktaran; Bacı, 2011). Places students spend much more time are schools. Özgür and Özbulut (2010) suggested that the best opportunity was schools to reduce and prevent violent behaviours, because children and teenagers were mostly affected and ultimately open to changes in their school years. Aggressiveness, violence, disturbance, violation, rudeness and use of force which we often observe at schools time spent much more, have remounted up at our schools in recent times, they disturb students subjected to violence at first, parents, teachers, school directors and society (Solak, 2007). Avcı (2010) informed that the ones engaged in violence were mothers-fathers, teachers and directors when psychological violence was subjected at our schools before, but at that time offenders and victims were students and physical violence was subjected more. A family which fulfills persons' fundamental needs such as feeding and feeling of confidence, protects and

develops physical and mental health, sometimes witnesses various types of violence (Çeliksaş, 2013). In literature, depending on the demographical factors, there are corresponding studies (Sağlam, 2016; Kılıç, 2011). Although our research has similar features to these studies, it is a fact that socio-demographical characteristics regarding students are among the resources feeding violence.

There are lots of reasons for that the students at any school tend to violent incidents, furthermore, the factors such as the students' characteristics at school, the size of school, the settlement area of school take precedence over the students' perceptions about violence (Angkaw, 2006). To prevent violence at schools, adults (parents, teachers, school directors, media managers, etc.) are required to display exemplary behaviours not involving violence (Altun et al. 2006). Balkıs et al. (2005) researched on the attitudes of students about violence at the secondary schools, determined that the students who had positive opinions and beliefs about violence, could have violence tendencies at a higher level than the other students.

As actors of violence, the secondary school students also try to overcome with the problems of youth period (adolescence) and adjust inter-family communication and relations (Yörükoğlu, 2004). Schools have an active structure which prepares students for life and lets them realize their potentials completely rather than an institution only giving cognitive education. Moreover, there are strongly considerable researches proving that school-based prevention programs reduce violent behaviours between the children at the school age, which is a significant point of organizing prevention practices at schools (Hahn et al. 2007).

Violence and violence focused behaviours not only do not affect an individual perpetrating violence and one's directed resource, but also disturb social sensitivity and inner conscience in a social structure whichin violence occurs. A research by Ünalmiş (2010) indicated that the students exposed to violence before exhibited more positive attitudes on violence. Maybe the worst thing is that violence and violence oriented anger, aggressiveness and virulent violence products are inured in a social structure. Aygüç (2015) suggested that there was a significant relation between the students' bullying tendencies and the exposure to violence in family. In a similar study, Deveci et al. (2008) advised the students to be understanding, lovely, respectful and tolerant with a view to preventing violence. The same research put the feelings of violence in order as fear, sorrow, revenge, excitement and bad feeling.

With developing technology; instruments such as computer, tablet and smart phone make children and young people share virtual, unreal and cool things in social networking sites. The relevant education program, field, type and content directly affect individuals' life quality as a whole, real shares and styles of feeling expressions are improved in these institutions in parallel with family education. Within this study, the

Sport High School students had lower violence tendencies than the other high school types since the students gave place to sportive activities in their lives and received sportive education.

References

1. Altun, S.A., Güneri, O.Y., Baker, Ö.E. (2006). Basındaki Yansımaları ile Okulda Şiddet, *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 24, pp, 12-21.
2. Angkaw, J.P. (2006). Addressing school violence in the 21st century. ED495737. Retrieved February 26, 2008, from ERIC Database.
3. Avcı, R., Güçray, S.S. (2010). Şiddet Davranışı Gösteren ve Göstermeyen Ergenlerin Ailelerinin Aile İşlevleri, Aile Bireylerine İlişkin Problemler, Öfke ve Öfke İfade Tarzları Açısından İncelenmesi, *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice* 10 (1), Winter 2010, 45-76.
4. Ayan, S. (2007). Aile İçinde Şiddete Uğrayan Çocukların Saldırganlık Eğilimleri, *Anadolu Psikiyatri Dergisi*; 8:206-214
5. Aygüç, F. (2015). Evaluation of bullying behaviors according to violence in family in secondary schools, *Yeditepe Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Eğitim Yönetimi ve Denetimi Anabilim Dalı, Yüksek Lisans Tezi.*
6. Bacı, S.D. (2011). Çocuk ve Ergenlerde Şiddet ve Saldırganlığın Önlenmesi. *Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İzmir: Doktora Tezi.*
7. Bakırcıoğlu, R. (2010). Çocuk ve Ergen Ruh Sağlığı. Ankara: Anı Yayıncılık.
8. Balcıoğlu, İ. (2003). Sporun Sosyolojisi ve Psikolojisi, İstanbul: Bilge Yayınları.
9. Balkıs, M., Duru, E., Buluş M. (2005). "Şiddete Yönelik Tutumların Özyeterlik, Medya, Şiddete Yönelik İnanç, Arkadaş Grubu ve Okula Bağlılık Duygusu İle İlişkisi." XV. Ulusal Eğitim Bilimleri Kongresi, Muğla.
10. Bandura, A. (1997). Social learning theory. *Practice Hall- New Jersey*, p. 22-36.
11. Başbakanlık Aile Araştırma Kurumu (1998). Aile içinde ve toplumsal alanda şiddet. *Bilim Serisi: 113. Ankara: Başbakanlık Basımevi.*
12. Budak, S. (2003). Psikoloji sözlüğü. 2. baskı. Ankara: Bilim ve Sanat Yayınları, S. 712.
13. Çabuk Kaya, N. (2006). "Şiddetin Sosyal Dinamikleri: Yoksulluk, İşsizlik ve Göç" Toplumsal Bir Sorun Olarak "Şiddet" Sempozyumu, Eğitim Sen. Bildiriler Kitabı.
14. Çeliktaş, M.G. (2013). Okuldaki Şiddet Olayları ile Aile İçi Şiddet İlişkisi. *Gazi Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara: Yüksek Lisans Tezi.*

15. Deveci, H., Karadaş, R., Yılmaz, F. (2008). İlköğretim Öğrencilerinin Şiddet Algıları, *Electronic Journal of Social Sciences*, V.7 N.24. (351-368).
16. Erkek, N.P. (2016). Yatılı ve Gündüzlü Eğitim Alan Ortaöğretim Öğrencilerinin Şiddet Eğilimleri İle Özgüvenleri Arasındaki İlişkinin İncelenmesi, Yüksek Lisans Tezi Çocuk Gelişimi ve Eğitimi Ana Bilim Dalı Gazi Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü.
17. Furlong, M.J., Morrison, G. (2000). The school in school violence: Definitions and facts. *Journal of Emotional & Behavioral Disorders*, 8, 71-82.
18. Gelinas, D.J. (2003). Witnessing violence: the effects on children and adolescents. (Ed. Joshua Miller,Irene R. Martin ve Gerald Schamess) *School violence and children in crisis: community and school interventions for social workers and counselors*. Denver: Love Publishing Company.
19. Gür, B. (2016) Evrensel bir sorun:Sporda Şiddet, Gazi Üniversitesi, Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Yüksek Lisans Tezi, s.3-10.
20. Hahn et al., (2007). Effectiveness of universal school-based programs to prevent violent andaggressive behavior: a systematic review. *American Fournal of Preventive Medicine*, 33,112-113.
21. Hanhan, A.A. (2012). Onarıcı Disiplin Modelinin Liselerde, Akran İstismarı ve Şiddeti Üzerindeki Etkilerinin İncelenmesi. Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İzmir: Doktora Tezi.
22. Hiçyılmaz, Y., İnci, M. A., & Seven, S. (2015). 7-10 Yaş Grubu Çocukların Şiddet Algılarının Resimler Aracılığı İle Sosyal Güçler Bağlamında İncelenmesi. *Ankara*. 503-508.
23. Kılıç, E.Z. (2011). Violent Behavior in Adolescence: Individual and Familial Factors, *Arc hi ves of Neu ropsy chi atr y* 2012; 49: 260-265, DOI: 10.4274/npa.y 6100.
24. Kılıçarslan, F. (2010). Çocuk ve Aile Sorunlarının Terapi ve Tedavisi. Ankara: Nobel.
25. Kocacık, F. (2007). Şiddet olgusu üzerine. *C.Ü. İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi* 2:1,1-7 <http://www.cumhuriyet.edu.tr/edergi/makale/88.pdf>. (Erişim tarihi: 28.09.2007).
26. Koçak, M., (2017). Examining the relationship between violent and nonviolent offending behaviours with childhood traumas and personality traits in young adults, Ankara Üniversitesi / Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü / Disiplinlerarası Adli Bilimler Anabilim Dalı, Yüksek Lisans tezi.
27. Memiş ve ark. (2013). Sağlık Çalışanları Şiddet Araştırması, Sağlık ve Sosyal Hizmet Çalışanları Sendikası, Sağlık-Sen Yayınları.

28. Nair, B. (2014). Ergenlerin Saldırganlık Davranışlarının Bazı Değişkenler Açısından Değerlendirilmesi. Cumhuriyet Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Sivas: Yüksek Lisans Tezi.
29. Özgür G., Yörükoğlu G., Baysan Arabacı L., (2011). High School Student's Perception of Violence, Level of Tendency to Violence and Effective Factor. Journal of Psychiatric Nursing 2011;2(2):53-6.
30. Özgür Ö., Özbulut M. (2010). Gençlik ve Şiddet Toplumsal Alanda Şiddetin Yükselişi, Ankara: Atatürk Kültür Merkezi Yayını.
31. Pekince, H. (2012). Ergenlerin Saldırganlık Düzeyleri İle Sosyal Aktivitelere Katılmaları Arasındaki İlişkinin İncelenmesi. İnönü Üniversitesi, Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Malatya: Yüksek Lisans Tezi.
32. Saban, A., Akbulut, M.G. (2012). İlköğretim birinci kademe öğrencilerinin şiddetle ilgili algılarının çizdikleri resimler aracılığıyla incelenmesi. Turkish Journal of Education, 1(1).
33. Sağlam, A. (2016). Ortaokul Öğrencilerinin Şiddet Eğilimleri İle Okula Bağlılık Düzeyleri Arasındaki İlişkinin İncelenmesi, Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü Eğitim Bilimleri Anabilim Dalı Rehberlik Ve Psikolojik Danışmanlık Programı Yüksek Lisans Tezi.
34. Solak, A. (2007). Okullarda Şiddet ve Çocuk Suçluluğu. Ankara, Pegem.
35. TBMM Araştırma Komisyon Raporu (2007). Türkiye'de ortaöğretime devam eden öğrencilerde ve ceza ve infaz kurumlarında bulunan tutuklu ve hükümlü çocuklarda şiddet ve bunu etkileyen etkenlerin saptanması. Araştırma Raporu. Ankara: 2007;(19-22):56-8.
36. TBMM Araştırma Komisyon Raporu (2013). Sağlık Çalışanlarına Yönelik Artan Şiddet Olaylarının Araştırılarak Alınması Gereken Önlemlerin Belirlenmesi, Yasama dönemi. 24, yasama yılı. 3, erişim adresi: <http://www.tbmm.gov.tr/sirasayi/donem24/yil01/ss454.pdf>, erişim tarihi: 22.02.2015. s. 454.
37. TDK, (2017). Şiddet nedir? <http://www.tdk.gov.tr/TKD.GTS.58f7789c9d8d38.43509176>.
38. Tor, H., Sargın, N. (2005). İlköğretim okullarının ikinci kademesinde okuyan öğrencilerin şiddet hakkındaki görüşleri. XIV. Ulusal Eğitim Bilimleri Kongresi, Denizli: 28-30 Eylül 2005, 751-756.
39. Ünalmiş, M., Şahin, R. (2012). Şiddete yönelik tutum ve okul zorbalığı. Uluslararası Cumhuriyet Eğitim Dergisi, 1(1): 63-71.
40. WHO (2002). Dünya sağlık raporu (şiddet ve sağlık dünya raporu). Web: [www.http://undp.unorg.tr/who/bulten/turk/bulten9.htm](http://undp.unorg.tr/who/bulten/turk/bulten9.htm)
41. Yönet, E., Çalık, F., Yaşartürk, F., Çimen, K. (2016). Lise Öğrencilerinin Rekreatif Etkinliklere Katılımları ile Saldırganlık- Şiddet Eğilimlerinin İncelenmesi,

International Journal of Science Culture and Sport, 4 (Special Issue 1) ISSN : 2148-1148 Doi : 10.14486/IntJSCS563.

42. Yörükoğlu, A. (2004). Gençlik Çağı Ruh Sağlığı ve Ruhsal Sorunlar. İstanbul: Özgür Yayınları.

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